

Irrational Use of Antibiotics During Covid19 Pandemic

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I. Abstract

Irrational use of antibiotics and the major complication of the rapid growth of antibiotic resistance are widely acknowledged. Irrational utilization of antibiotics includes prescription of incorrect dose, duration, route of administration, and frequency of regimen and are influenced by certain interrelated factors and drivers. The major complications of irrational antibiotic use are antibiotic resistance with an increase in poorer health outcomes, increased healthcare costs, longer hospitalization, and higher mortality. The irrational use of antibiotics has accelerated during the COVID-19 pandemic and has led to severe peri- and post-hospitalization complications. Although the usage of antibiotics in COVID-19 patients has not been widely studied in the literature, beneficial outcomes have been reported in treating bacterial co-infections and superinfections. The rational and prudent use of antibiotics is required and the approach to achieving the goal and addressing the challenges must be effectively outlined. Clinical pharmacists are indispensable in promoting the selection and appropriate use of antibiotics. The current review describes the causes and complications associated with the irrational use of antibiotics in COVID-19 patients and addresses the major public health concerns.

Key-words: Irrational use, antibiotics, COVID-19 pandemic, clinical pharmacist, AMR (Antimicrobial resistance)

II. Introduction

Antibiotics are an important part of modern healthcare. Generally, antibiotics are used to treat bacterial infections but due to their antiviral and anti-inflammatory activities and their ability to prevent secondary infections, they are largely being misused in the treatment of COVID-19, a viral infection caused by SARS-CoV2 where unawareness can lead to misuse of antibiotics which could cause severe complications like antimicrobial resistance, toxicity and Clostridium difficile infection. The present narrative review was developed to discuss the causes and complications of the irrational use of antibiotics employed in COVID patients.

III. Antibiotics and Covid-19

Irrational use of antibiotics in clinical practice can begin a pandemic of antimicrobial resistance to microorganisms. WHO identified India as one of the top countries with higher rates of antibiotic resistance in the world with proven reports of irrational use of antibiotics resulting in increased incidence of antimicrobial resistance [1]. COVID-19 is a viral infection caused by the recently discovered coronavirus. A zoonotic infection was discovered in Wuhan, China, in late December 2019. Though initial investigations reported animal-to-human transmission, subsequent investigations have also declared human-human transmissions through close contact with an infected person and even through coughing and sneezing because the virus generally spreads via airborne zoonotic droplets. The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared COVID-19 a pandemic due to its rapid global spread [2]. COVID-19 is a pathogenic virus that can cause gastrointestinal and pneumonia-like symptoms including diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, cough, cold, and shortness of breath, it affects the human population where elderly and people with comorbid disease conditions or lower immune functions can become severe cases [3]. Antibiotics are often ineffective against viral infections. The goal of including antibiotics in the treatment regimen in the clinical management of COVID-19 is to either treat any bacterial co-infection associated with COVID-19 or to harness its possible antiviral activity. As no clinical trials

have been undertaken to justify the use of empiric antibiotics in patients, there is currently no evidence-based transparent review to monitor the bacterial co-infection associated with COVID-19 disease [4].

Some antibiotics have been scrutinized for their antiviral activities such as Fluoroquinolones to bind to SARS-Cov2 protease and block replication. The benefits of beta-lactams in critically ill patients with COVID-19 infection are being investigated; however, more clinical trials are needed to thoroughly evaluate the results. COVID-19 infection can result in an excessive inflammatory response and cytokine production; however, some macrolides, such as azithromycin and clarithromycin, have anti-inflammatory actions and may be beneficial in COVID-19 infection. In viral infections such as Influenza, Zika, or H1N1, Azithromycin has been proven to inhibit viral replication.

As the initial wave of the COVID-19 pandemic arrived, it was noticed that the majority of the patients admitted with COVID-19 had been prescribed broad-spectrum antibiotics. Suspicion of bacterial co-infection and the presence of superinfection lead to antibiotic use. Antibiotic use in COVID-19 patients has been described in more than 70% of the cases. More recent literature and studies have validated those superinfections and co-infections caused by bacteria are very rare, literature also suggests that bacterial co-infection is so rare that it occurs in less than 10% of patients overall and the lack of evidence is leading to irrational use of antibiotics in patients with COVID-19 infection [5].

The rational and prudent utilization of antibiotics is required and the approaches for achieving the goal and addressing the challenges must be well communicated. The lack of awareness among the general public regarding the inappropriate use of antibiotics must be addressed with a good monitoring and surveillance system. Standard treatment recommendations have been generated in developing nations stressing minimizing the use of antibiotics by improving the quality of water, sanitation, and immunization. The goal is when they are not necessary. Two approaches have been stimulated to reduce/prevent the spread of antibiotic resistance - 1) improved targeting of antibiotics and 2) comprehensive immunization through vaccination against pneumonia and H. Influenza B virus. In hospital settings, infection control committee measures such as isolation rooms, hand washing, use of PPE, and in-service training for physicians to improve prescription behaviour can be implemented to reduce the transmission of infections.

The aim of clinical pharmacists includes functions necessary to discharge a set of social responsibilities regarding the proper therapeutic use of drugs (prescribing, dispensing, and administration), documenting professional services, direct contact with patients, and review of drugs along with education, consultation, and counselling. The objective lies in ensuring the patient's optimal well-being resulting from the secure and sensible use of drugs. The goals are to ensure the appropriate maintenance of documentation related to medical incidents to maximize patient compliance with drug use [6]. Antimicrobial resistance is a natural phenomenon, and many factors contribute to its emergence and spread. One of the major factors of AMR threat is the irrational use of antibiotics [7]. Irrational antibiotic usage includes the prescription of improper dosages, polypharmacy, self-medication practices, off-label use, inappropriate ROA, and antibiotic overuse/abuse [8]. These elements increase the exposure of bacteria to suboptimal levels of antibiotics resulting in therapeutic inefficiency and facilitating resistance against the drug [9]. Irrational use of antibiotics has been emerging as a global threat to healthcare in escalating numbers in both developed and developing nations and is estimated to be 80% in community settings of low- and middle-income countries that lack policies and restrictions [10]. The outcomes are generally associated with longer hospitalization, poor health outcomes, increased cost to patient/government, and higher mortality and spread. Numerous pieces of literature have reported the prevalence of unjustified usage of antibiotics in developed nations, Southern and Eastern Europe have recorded 30% and 19% of irrational antibiotic use respectively. Other studies conducted in the Southern region (Greece, Italy, Malta, and Spain) have reported similar results. Northern countries like Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, and the Netherlands have reported a prevalence of 3% and 6% in central countries [11]. Recent study reports from Tanzania have observed 88.8% of irrational antibiotic purchases with more non-prescription use and incomplete dosage purchases and concluded a relatively higher prevalence.

Antibiotics used to treat viral infections can significantly enhance the risk of resistance and allergic reactions. Irrational use of antibiotics in COVID-19 can lead to many serious complications such as antimicrobial resistance, Clostridium difficile infection, Renal and hepatic toxicities, and Adverse drug reactions. Adherence to guidelines needs a thorough understanding of antibiotics and therapeutic outcomes. Clinical pharmacists are indispensable in promoting the selection and appropriate use of antibiotics depending on provable microbiological examinations in paediatrics with special care. Additionally, monitoring with pertinent intervals with verifiable use of rational dose antibiotics can result in precise therapy to avoid complications.

IV. Drivers for Irrational Use of Antibiotics in Covid

A. *Lack of awareness among the general public*

COVID-19 being a lethal pandemic has instilled disastrous effects all over the globe including insecurity, panic, depression, and confusion with lack of awareness being the major con making it even more complicated. Millions of people are uneducated and isolated, unaware of the facilities and information provided by the government regarding COVID-19 including antibiotic use [12].

The education and understanding about the antibiotics among the public is a strong element in determining the irrational use of antibiotics. An important factor in determining the irrational use of antibiotics is public education and awareness of these drugs. According to a study, 44 percent of Europeans are unaware that antibiotics cannot treat cold and flu symptoms, and 57 percent are unaware that antibiotics cannot treat viruses [13].

B. *Availability of OTC Antibiotics*

Availability of antibiotics without a prescription leads to irrational use of antibiotics as consumption of antibiotics without a proper diagnosis can result in antimicrobial resistance. A study conducted in Bangladesh revealed that antibiotics were largely consumed by COVID-19-positive and suspected patients without receiving a prescription from a qualified doctor. 63% of the Bangladeshi COVID-19 patients quarantined at home with mild or asymptomatic infection consumed one or more antibiotic agents [14].

C. *Impact of left-over medications and self-medication use*

The use of leftover antibiotics can pose a serious threat of complications. Unawareness and panic caused by the COVID-19 pandemic can influence suspected COVID-19 patients to self-medicate with left-over antibiotics which can aid in antimicrobial resistance and adverse effects associated with irrational usage of antibiotics. A study showed that 44% of the people with leftover antibiotics accepted that they are preserving the antibiotics to use them in the future [15].

D. *Knowledge, Attitude, and Perception of healthcare workers regarding antibiotic use in covid*

Healthcare providers are responsible to choose and select the appropriate antibiotics for the treatment. The knowledge, attitude, and perceptivity of the prescribers towards the usage of antibiotics and the antimicrobial resistance associated with it determine the rational use of antibiotics. Misinterpretation and poor diagnostic approach can lead to irrational antibiotic use.

According to one study, antibiotics were given to 90 percent of patients hospitalized in the medicine department for no apparent reason. The most commonly used antibiotics were beta-lactams (72 percent), macrolides (60.2%), and fluoroquinolones (13.3 percent) [16].

E. *Lack of Patient-Doctor Interaction*

Due to social distancing and lockdowns amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, the treatment and clinical information from the doctors is being provided digitally through video conferences and television to the patients who are not hospitalized or quarantined to diminish the risk of exposure to others. Due to the absence of face-to-face interactions, sometimes patients are not able to understand the treatment, and patients might skip a dose or adjust the dose by themselves to feel better, such conditions can lead to irrational antibiotic use. Conditions of some patients can become serious as the infection progresses in the home-isolated patients. Home isolation can also postpone initial treatment and hospitalization of quarantined patients which can result in death in severe cases.

V. Complications of Irrational Antibiotics Use

A. *Antimicrobial Resistance*

The hasty development of resistant bacteria across the globe is threatening the effectiveness of antibiotics. Scarcity in the new drug development by the pharma companies because of diminished economic enticement along with misuse and overuse of antibiotics have been enhancing antibiotic resistance. In 2013, the CDC announced the 'post-antibiotic era'. In 2014, the World Health Organization informed antimicrobial resistance catastrophe is becoming critical. US Public Health, Institute of Medicine, and Federal Interagency Task Force announced 15 multi-drug-resistant bacteria as a considerable hazard to antimicrobial resistance [17]. As per the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, each year, 25,000 individuals in Europe die as a consequence of resistant infection. Antibiotic resistance also results in a rise in healthcare expenses [18]. Amidst gram-positive bacteria, resistant strains of *S. aureus* and *Enterococcus* are becoming very dangerous as MRSA

wipes out more Americans every year than HIV prevalence. Commonly used antibiotics are resistant to respiratory disease-causing microbes like *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and other pathogens including Vancomycin-resistant enterococci due to constantly increasing drug resistance while gram-negative microbes are disastrous and alarming as they are becoming resistant to approximately all the antibiotic choice accessible. The development of multi-drug-resistant gram-negative bacilli is the most severe which has impacted practice in every discipline of medicine, these infections usually arise at the hospital and are usually caused by Enterobacteriaceae, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter* [19].

Antimicrobial resistance became one of the biggest public health issues in the world following the COVID-19 pandemic. Antibiotics may be given to COVID-19 patients for the following reasons, 1) COVID-19 symptoms can be similar to bacterial pneumonia, thus the empirical treatment 2) Antibiotics have antiviral properties 3) Secondary bacterial infection prophylaxis [20]. A study conducted in Milan, Italy estimates that 66.7% of COVID-19 patients received antibiotics, whereas studies conducted in Barcelona, Spain reported 80% [21]. COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU repeatedly receive antibiotics based on the seriousness of the disease and lab markers for inflammation even in the absence of secondary bacterial infection. A meta-analysis conducted during the first semester of the pandemic revealed that antibiotics were given to 75 percent of COVID-19 patients worldwide [22]. Surprisingly, a study found that only 8% of 72 percent of COVID-19 patients who used antibiotics had bacterial infection [23].

All these types of data support the escalation of irrational use of antibiotics in COVID-19 management and the resistance of secondary bacteria to several antibiotics. Additionally, antimicrobial resistance was found among 84% of COVID-19 patients suffering from secondary bacterial infection and these microbes when isolated showed resistance to Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, Fluoroquinolones, Piperacillin-tazobactam, Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and more than 64% resistance to 3rd Gen Cephalosporins and Carbapenems [24]. Another study on COVID-19 patients showed that nosocomial microbes were resistant to Cephalosporins, Fluoroquinolones, and Beta-lactams. A fungal infection caused by 'Candida auris' was found associated with COVID-19 patients in India and exhibited resistance against antifungal drugs like Amphotericin-B and Fluconazole [25]. More antibiotics are being developed and manufactured by pharmaceutical industries during the COVID-19 pandemic and increased risk of irrational antibiotic use in patients. Inappropriate waste management can exacerbate the prevalence of antimicrobial resistance [26]. The COVID-19 pandemic has further escalated the prevalence of antimicrobial resistance with a significant increase in healthcare costs and could lead to a disastrous situation of common infections being fatal in the future. Expedition of COVID-19 vaccination can help in diminishing the prevalence of antimicrobial resistance as vaccines can also lessen the hospitalization rate [27].

The aim is not just to limit antibiotic use but to rationalize it as well, it can be achieved by spreading awareness through educational campaigns and practicing antimicrobial stewardship to bring positive change in the knowledge, attitude, and perception of healthcare professionals and the general public about rational antibiotic use.

B. Clostridium Difficile Infection

Clostridium difficile is a serious condition more frequently causing nosocomial antibiotic-associated diarrhoea with increasing incidence, morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs worldwide. Centre for Disease Control and Prevention has identified *C. Diff* to be one of the five urgent antibiotic resistance threats. Antibiotic use is not indicated in *C. Diff* colonization and is only to be treated in the presence of CDI with symptoms ranging from mild foul-smelling watery diarrhoea to pseudomembranous colitis and toxic megacolon. Although CDI is developed as a consequence of irrational antibiotic exposure, especially in the elderly population. It is estimated that approximately 72% of COVID-19 patients are treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics and respiratory quinolones for infection prophylaxis [28].

Other factors such as alcohol consumption, previous hospitalizations, previous exposure to antibiotic treatments, and urban residents are found to be contributing to the development of *C. Diff* in COVID patients and require larger doses of vancomycin and susceptible to recurrent disease [29]. The lack of high-level evidence in early management recommendations includes empirical antibiotic regimens leading to huge amounts of antimicrobial consumption such as azithromycin and ceftriaxone. Between 1st Sep 2020 and 30th Apr 2021, a total of 2065 COVID cases were reported in an Infectious Diseases Clinic in Romania and reported that 40 cases of CDI including 32 hospital-onset cases and 8 community-onset and healthcare-associated cases [30].

COVID-19 hospitalization can significantly alter the gut microbiota and also is at risk of serious antibiotic-acquired adverse effects of HA-CDI. A retrospective case-control study including 8402 COVID-19 patients showed a consequential link between antibiotic use and CDI. More than average patients who developed CDI in the hospital setting were elderly (mean=79 years) with various comorbidities and only 2.6% of patients with CDI had no comorbidities. The mortality rate was significantly higher for COVID-19 and CDI, at 28%, compared to 5% for the general population of CDI only [31]. The risk factors involved in *C. Diff* co-infection

include disease comorbidities, consumption of NSAIDs, antibiotic therapy, and increased age group. NSAIDs such as aspirin and ibuprofen are widely used for pain management and fever symptoms in COVID patients and along with immunomodulators can potentially enhance the development of bacterial infections and are found to be particularly prominent in the elderly (>65 years of age) [32]. Since the clinical features of patients with COVID include fever, cough, and lung infiltrations which resemble bacterial pneumonia they are treated with appropriate antimicrobials during hospitalization. Otherwise, are also treated with antivirals, heparin therapy for hypoxia, convalescent plasma transfusion therapy, and also corticosteroids for the management of inflammatory response [33]. Co-infection with *C. Diff* with COVID-19 results in a higher mortality rate with poor therapeutic outcomes. Case reports have also studied the complications of COVID and *C. Diff* resulting in the development of acute portal vein thrombosis with local/systemic prothrombotic risk factors involved [34].

According to scientific literature, increased concern about hand hygiene, sterilized environment, proper patient isolation, and duly use of PPE during the initial period of a pandemic have been found to decrease healthcare-associated infections of CDI. In regard to the increase in irrational use of antibiotics and significant GI symptoms reported in COVID patients, prolonged attention to symptom monitoring is mandatory and following established therapeutic guidelines of antimicrobial stewardship should remain alert for unsolicited adverse reactions.

C. Hepatotoxicity and Nephrotoxicity

Acute kidney injury and liver injury, in addition to respiratory failure, are two serious complications of covid 19 that increase the risk of mortality and morbidity. The causes of divulging include direct cytopathogenic effects, secondary damage caused by the coexistence of inflammatory responses, or the effect of the patient's drug therapy. According to studies, nearly 14-53 percent of COVID-19-positive patients have experienced acute liver and acute kidney injury, or both [35]. The presence of chronic conditions and off-label antibiotic use are the underlying risk factors that exacerbate liver and kidney damage in covid 19 patients. During COVID-19, there was an increase in the irrational use of azithromycin and other broad-spectrum antibiotics which were found to be associated with AKI and liver damage in vulnerable populations.

Antibiotic-induced hepatotoxicity is usually asymptomatic, transient, and only causes minor hepatic dysfunction. However, in rare cases, acute liver failure has resulted in significant morbidity and death. Hepatocellular injury, cholestasis, stenosis, and zonal injury are all common side effects of antibiotics, all of which impair liver function. Irrational antibiotic use in COVID-19 patients can cause hepatotoxicity, which can worsen the infection's direct liver damage. The presence of ACE-2 receptors on cholangiocytes and hepatocytes has been demonstrated, suggesting that the liver could be a potential access point for SARS-COV-2, resulting in direct liver damage and inflammation/immune reactions manifested as fibrosis and liver dysfunction [36]. The high expression of the ACE 2 proteins, which are the main binding sites for SARS-COV-2, human kidneys are believed to be a major target of the novel SARS-COV-2 infection. Acute proximal tubular injury, endothelial damage, hemosiderin deposition, pigment casts related to rhabdomyolysis, and inflammation are common symptoms of kidney injury noted in COVID patients [37]. Off-label and irrational use of antibiotics is studied to be linked to intratubular crystal deposition, interstitial nephritis, and proximal and distal tubulopathy exacerbating the direct effects caused by SARS-COV-2 infection [38].

A few other studies have also found that severe COVID-19 patients have elevated liver functions, which can lead to serious complications and irrational use of antibiotics exacerbates these direct effects. To avoid complications, it is recommended that antibiotics must be used with caution as per protocols and guidelines which are specialized in the COVID-19 pandemic and a rational manner in COVID-19 patients. Antibiotic rationing should be promoted in the treatment of COVID-19 patients to avoid further organ damage and serious long-term complications.

D. Adverse drug reactions

Antibiotics are widely used for treating bacterial infections and preventing bacterial multiplication. Antibiotics, while effective against bacterial infections, can produce adverse drug reactions in people due to hypersensitivity reactions and drug-drug interactions [39]. Any undesirable consequences from medication that result in physical, mental, or functional injuries are known as adverse drug reactions (ADRs). Antibiotics are responsible for up to 40.9 percent of ADRs and are linked to several significant side effects. Symptoms such as diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, rashes, and gastrointestinal distress are among the most prevalent adverse drug reactions. Numerous factors influence the severity, including drug properties such as duration of usage and strength and the patient's immune system. Type A and Type B reactions are frequently used to categorize these reactions. In most circumstances, Type A reactions are predictable and are caused by pharmacological side effects and drug interactions. Type B reactions are typically unexpected and might be immune or non-immune-mediated [40].

Antibiotics are responsible for the occurrence of ADRs and have been associated with longer hospitalization, and higher medical expenses in hospitalized patients. A retrospective cohort study at a tertiary care hospital in South Korea showed antibiotics as a leading source of ADRs and they concluded penicillin and quinolones as the most common antibiotics leading to ADRs [41]. Because of the urgent need for effective COVID-19 treatments, less attention may have been devoted to their safety during the global emergency about adverse drug reactions of antibiotics; although the prevalence of adverse drug reactions of antibiotics in COVID-19 patients has not been thoroughly investigated, evidence from observational studies show that it may be considerably immense in the population [42].

Adverse drug reactions of antibiotics can include gastrointestinal effects like vomiting, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, loss of appetite, and bloating as well as allergy-related skin disorders such as rashes, angioedema, pruritic, and urticaria and haematological disorders like anaemia, thrombocytopenia. According to one study, 410 of the 1273 clindamycin adverse medication events were gastrointestinal, 102 were infectious, 19 were immune system related, and 366 were allergy-related skin disorders. Clostridium difficile infections were found to be common adverse drug reactions of clindamycin [43].

By suppressing erythropoiesis, linezolid, amphotericin B, chloramphenicol, and ganciclovir can cause anaemia. Chloramphenicol usually causes reversible anaemia, which is likely when medication concentrations in the blood exceed the recommended limit. Agranulocytosis and leukopenia caused by antibiotics are usually reversible. Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, most β -lactams, vancomycin, macrolides, clindamycin, chloramphenicol, flucytosine, and amphotericin B are anti-infectives that might cause neutropenia or agranulocytosis [44].

Antibiotic-induced thrombocytopenia can be caused by immune-mediated platelet death or by a decreased number of megakaryocytes. The antibacterial oxazolidinone linezolid is the most likely to destroy platelets. Penicillins are frequently linked to defective platelet aggregation, a method by which some antibiotics can cause bleeding, and this is most probably the case with penicillin G and advanced-generation penicillin. In the ICU, drug-induced ototoxicity can lead to hearing loss or vestibular dysfunction. Erythromycin and azithromycin can produce bilateral hearing loss or labyrinthine malfunction, which is usually reversible after 2 weeks. Ototoxicity or vestibular dysfunction is caused by aminoglycosides in 10% to 22% of patients, and this ototoxicity or vestibular dysfunction may be permanent. Penicillin, imipenem ciprofloxacin, and other β -lactam antibiotics can cause hallucinations, twitching, and seizures. Macrolides are widely used to treat COVID-19 infection as along with antibacterial properties, they possess immune-suppressive and antiviral activity. Azithromycin can induce gastrointestinal adverse effects as well as hepatotoxicity (cholestatic jaundice) [45]. It is very important to diagnose, differentiate, and monitor the adverse drug reactions caused by antibiotics as they can enhance mortality and morbidity risks, irrational use of antibiotics should be avoided in healthcare settings by assessing the adverse effects and medication therapy management.

VI. Conclusion

The complications associated with the irrational use of antibiotics result in antibiotic resistance and severely impact health and economic outcomes. The comprehensive review reports various drivers of concern to be addressed and significant complications requiring immediate action in the course of the COVID-19 pandemic. Clinical pharmacist identifies and develop standard guidelines with relevant pharmacokinetic data to provide sufficient information to improve antibiotic use in healthcare settings. Programs and policies in initiating awareness schemes such as antimicrobial stewardship programs tailored for COVID-19 patients must be developed and should be well monitored for deviations in clinical practice.

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